

Dependent Interconnecting Realities

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Abstract

This paper aims to investigate the potential of an interconnecting representational chainmail reality. The umbrella term of spacetime and quantum entanglement is this dimension. It is characterized by a nonrelativistic specialization of phase waves, which emphasizes that they are a relativistic concept. The properties of de Broglie waves' frequency, wavelength, and velocity are found under a Lorentz transformation.

Introduction

Reality is not a standalone that happens to experience entanglement; rather, it is a chainmail-like data processing system that requires multiple components to function from a separate reality. Co-dependent realities refer to the connection between the nature of our experiences and perceptions. This concept means that our realities are not isolated, but rather influenced and dependent on the realities of others experiences and actions of one person can have a direct impact on the experiences and actions of another, creating a web of interconnectedness that shapes our understanding of the world. Today we will discuss why this is true and the procedures used to carry this theory out.

Time

What would time look like in a world where chain dependency was common? We bring this up concerning time travel and/or other content of rifts that can affect dimensional collapse or warping. We must account for the inconsistency of stability because of how delicate these connections are. the Möbius strip answered this question. How does this enable true time travel between dependent realities? (time travel is possible it's just very chaotic)

In the circle then, and in the area intersecting with the chain link, which would enable academic penetration of the alternative chain, but with different traps than knowing if a person is alive. Rips and cracks can accelerate parts past the speed of light if the chains are punctured. Relativity, system titles, and mortals. However, we must look at the time itself; according to Albert Einstein, "Time is what clocks measure" (Dowden, B. (2021). Time. Online Encyclopedia of Gospel. <https://iep.utm.edu/time/>). and we're asking the meaning of the noun "time." A first step in this direction might be to filter the difference between what it means and what it refers to. The temporary word changes its reference every minute, not its meaning. Gottfried Leibniz. (Dowden, B. (2021). Time. Online Gospel Encyclopedia. <https://iep.utm.edu/time/>) Grammatically, we must understand that "time" is not a noun but a concept.

As Herman Minoski stated, "The correct way to understand relativity is to say that time is a fixed, non-spatial dimension of space, and time has no existence independent of space. Einstein agreed." (Dowden, B. (2021). Time. Online Gospel Encyclopedia. <https://iep.utm.edu/time/>) This is important because time is no longer considered a dimension or essentially independent, meaning that time depends on some other factor, similar to titles or spacetime itself. Eisenstein later discovered "that real spacetime is dynamic and not static. That is, its structure, like its

pattern, changes over time when the matter-energy distribution changes. According to special reciprocity and Newton's proposal, spacetime is not dynamic; it remains the same regardless of what matter and energy do. " Dowden, B.(2021). Time. Gospel's Online Encyclopedia. <https://iep.utm.edu/time/>) Time therefore now depends on matter and energy to remain static as a concept; space-time can rotate. We do not know the real curvature of our space. However, there is still good empirical evidence, obtained in the 1990s, that the total cosmic curvature of space is approximately zero but is evolving to a positive value." Dowden, B. (2021). Time. Online Encyclopedia of Gospel. <https://iep.utm.edu/time/>. Significant numbers and imaginary numbers are now most likely to be positive in this "space." However, these dependent realities should be negative because it is a "photographed" image that constantly spreads and destroys itself. Although we do not know whether these states would be deformed, we know that the other limitations would be negative because the state they now inhabit is a plane we cannot access unless we separate our mortal matter and parts, and they also reconnect.

Not to mention, we start immersing ourselves in scenarios where we cannot understand what we are witnessing. Another question arises: "How do we know that it is not straight up or down to the left or right?" Absolute space is ridiculous because, according to Leibniz, it ignores the principle of sufficient reason. He also argues that there would be no sufficient reason to create a macrocosm other than two dimensions to the left since no region of space is distinguishable from something else (see "Correspondence with Clarke," the fourth book of Leibniz). (Similar problems can affect the generalization of absolute time.) ". Burnham, D. (2010). Gottfried Leibniz Metaphysics. Online Gospel Encyclopedia. <https://iep.utm.edu/leib-met/#H7>) So these other dependent realities are not just filled with chaotic figures and unfathomable forms far from the chain mail; we at least see that as its

primary form. This gives an interesting cobweb substance that also flows into an electromagnetic wave that acts and reacts to itself. In summary, these realities are interdependent and highly dependent on each other to remain stable in a chaotic state that is constantly affecting and tearing it apart. Although time travel is possible, we cannot ignore the fact that what we are witnessing would be intractable in three dimensions.

The space

When we think of dependent realities we must also include the idea of space. How would the space act and how exactly is it stable with the current twist that allows for dependency and would it also have a vacuum effect? According to the study made by Chunjun Cao, Sean M. Carroll, and Spyridon Michalakis,

Figure 1. Decrease of Entanglement of Point A-B with Distance [6]

” spacetime itself seems to self-emerge from the entanglement. They “examined how space can emerge from an abstract quantum state in Hilbert space, and how something like Einstein’s equation is a natural consequence of this bulk emergent gravity program”. (Zhu, P. Y. (2021) This is very important because it seems that space branches off of the entanglement. This is why we use quantum entanglement as a good vector or idea of reference for dependent realities. This makes everything simpler and in the end easier to comprehend in the long run. Quoting this time “What is more, the model allows a classical wormhole to emerge as a result,

which deepens the relation between quantum entanglement and spacetime, since this is an unexpected feature without putting the two entities together. “Lengths and other geometric quantities are determined by entanglement”, and “gravity appears to arise from quantum mechanics naturally”. Self-emergence of spacetime from quantum mechanics implies a new relation between gravity and quantum mechanics.” (Zhu, P. Y. (2021) With all this combined it’s clear that gravity and space are branching off of entanglement which is exactly what’s happening in dependent realities.

Figure 2. Entanglement between two regions and the curvature [9]

But what about gravity? How would gravity react to co-dependent realities? According to (Dr. Christopher S. Baird) “gravity can form waves. Gravitational waves are ripples in spacetime that travel through the universe. If you think of gravity as a force acting at a distance” (Dr.Christopher (*Can Gravity Form Waves?*, 2018). This goes along with the domino theory where like “waves” everything requires a stimulus that travels in waves to the end. This would in return happen over and over again as a different stimulus each time around. But the main reason this occurs is during travel warping due to relativity.

Domino theory

A stimulus that travels through waves to make a change in the second spectrum. The reason it travels in fields is due to relativity which is “a warping or curvature of space and time. All objects warp space-time. When other objects travel through this warped spacetime, they travel along curved paths. These curved paths look like they result from a force being exerted on the objects when in reality they result from spacetime itself being warped.”

Where does everything start?

Well, it starts with a field where elementary particles assemble into twenty-four unique fields each with their specialty being positive and negatively charged.

Field according to (Dr. David Tong) “Field is a quantity defined at every point of space and time While classical particle mechanics deals with a finite number of generalized coordinates $q_a(t)$, indexed by a label a , in field theory we are interested in the dynamics of fields where both a and $\vec{x}$ are considered as labels. Thus we are dealing with a system with an infinite number of degrees of freedom — at least one for each point $\vec{x}$ in space.” But what if these fields were two and could interact with each other according to (Dr. Tong) “the truth particle states in the interacting theory through renormalization., suitably interpreted, remains true even in the interacting theory, taking into account the swarm of virtual particles surrounding asymptotic states. This is the correct way to consider scattering.” This then kicks off matter creation which sparks two realities needing each other for survival.. Later a link is formed where black holes and white holes could occur as well as various other anomalies. This creates dependency for stability which later is where dependent realities form.

Quantum entanglement and spin relation to dependent realities

We can assume the ground state would be the entangled state of both. This creates a pull-push sequence that is important regarding entanglement; this creates a twisted treadmill

track that provides infinite possibilities. This of course would cause Hilbert space which is a very small dimension (which is the next step) that would cause higher dimensional figures and color spaces but by theory

Materials

Laser pointer and a mirror/glass window with fishing line

But how exactly does it work?

Similar to data processing it acts much like a computer; it manipulates “raw data” just like elementary particles in a quantum field. “through the CPU and memory to output devices, and formatting or transformation of output. Any use of computers to perform defined operations on data can be included under data processing.” (Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2021, May 4). The CPU stands for the current dependency link between realities both practically being the heart of the main process the output would be the realities of the changes occurring in both but with different effects on each.

The experiment

Based on the double slit experiment laser light was used to imitate a photon beam that could bend. The design has a helix of fishing lines that crosses the light and a mirror that replicates the pattern seen in the space. It was first started with only one strand of fishing line,

(fishing line allows traveling through a complex surface such as a helix which is why it is used). One was used to simulate waves at the pure boundary of the double-slit experiment. Which proved successful in showing. The reason for the laser pointer is for its ability to provide a polarized beam that easily could be manipulated and for safety because an electron gun is not very safe. Aside from that the experiment's purpose helps prove dependent realities much like how mine is dependent on the helix to form and the slit experiment “The principle of interference is that two waves coming from different sources to one point superpose in that point. Interference is used to demonstrate the wave nature of the investigated physical phenomenon.” (Young T, 2022)

Procedure

Here the double helix is formed causing distortions but when witnessed in the mirror it sparks the idea of reality chaining. This effect recreates the hooking of all realities and each being codependent on the other to survive. This is then broken up into waves which we call de Broglie's waves which emphasize “ that they are a relativistic concept. The properties of de Broglie waves' frequency, wavelength, and velocity are found under a Lorentz transformation. A nonrelativistic specialization of phase waves is obtained, and the appropriate frequency,

wavelength, and velocity are defined.” This is what we perceive as the waves and assume them to be which is used multiple times through the equations

Result

. In the end, the experiment proved successful showing the expected outcome of a representational chainmail dimension that connects.

Timeline

Normal conversation would have a problem it would be able to perceive the future and the past at the same time. It would go like this (the receipt, the decept, the incept, and the except). So when we think of a subject we must also think beyond the subject as well. It would sound much like this-

[21:38] Abaris Brautigan: I think it's interesting being a woman, but I worked so hard to cultivate that strange signature appearance of mine...

[21:38] Lyr Lobo: hehehe

[21:38] Lyr Lobo: we all get "rushed"

[21:39] Lyr Lobo: it is a data error

[21:39] Lyr Lobo: even women...with the brown hair under our prim hair

[21:40] Abaris Brautigan: Yes--I've got the brown hair at the moment. And earrings even!!

[21:41] Lyr Lobo: hehe

(Smyth, R. (2017)

See how the conversation repeats at the end let alone how robotic it sounds. While this conversation is present in a virtual environment it provides a good example of the four

types of conversation mentioned earlier. How would the space look, however? We will assume the space to be a non-Euclidean space with advanced geometries

Topology in a co-dependent space

Topology is a “branch of mathematics, sometimes referred to as “rubber sheet geometry,” in which two objects are considered equivalent if they can be continuously deformed into one another through such motions in space as bending, twisting, stretching, and shrinking while disallowing tearing apart or gluing together parts. “(Carlson, 2019). Which is the

Klein bottle or Mobius strip

however we are looking at

topology in a reality where

codependency is the goal.

Which is what we expect it to

look like here. This is a reality

mesh link this is what our reality

would look like if codependent.

The linking line is invisible and the dimension is aligned in a chainmail link.

Hidden Dimensions in Real Space

Two normal dimensions with six extra dimensions curled up in Calabi-Yau spaces

Hypothesis

We Have Observed that co-dependent realities are possible and unstable by laser pointer and a mirror. We Wish we could prove the dangers behind a reality if it is co-dependent and how it would explain multiple phenomena in our reality For the segment in person. This will lead us can recreate a small chain of dependent realities by measuring how many "realities" are present. The test will run for six months to provide a small chain.

Summary

Time

- True time travel between dependant realities is made possible by the Möbius strip, which offers insight into what time might look like in a world where chain dependence is prevalent. Time is a concept rather than a term, and it is currently seen to depend on other things like space-time. Because of the constant changes in the distribution of matter and energy, real spacetime is dynamic.
- Space's overall cosmic curvature is currently almost zero but is gradually increasing to a positive number. These dependent realities, on the other hand, ought to be negative as they are a "photographed" image that perpetually dissipates and multiplies. These

realities are in a state of perpetual chaos that is influencing and pulling them apart, and they are heavily dependent on one another to be stable.

- Absolute space is absurd because there would be no incentive to develop a macrocosm other than two dimensions to the left. After all, no portion of space is identifiable from something else. Consequently, in three dimensions, what we observe in these worlds would be unmanageable.
- Although it is chaotic and would need us to immerse ourselves in situations we do not fully comprehend, time travel is conceivable. In addition to being full of erratic shapes and incomprehensible patterns, these other dependent realities also flow into an electromagnetic wave that acts and responds to itself. In short, we would observe something unmanageable in three dimensions since these realities are always influencing and pulling one another apart.

Space

- This is why we use quantum entanglement as a good vector or reference idea for dependent realities. Quote this time: "In addition, the model allows for a classical wormhole, which deepens the relationship between quantum entanglement and space-time, as this is an unexpected feature without bringing both entities together. The self-emergence of spacetime from quantum mechanics implies a new relationship between gravity and quantum mechanics.» (Chu, P.Y. (2021) With all of this combined, it is clear that gravity and space originate from entanglement, which is exactly what happens in dependent realities. This is consistent with the domino theory which states that, like a "wave," everything needs a stimulus that travels in the wave until its end.

Field

- Field according to (Dr. David Tong) “A field is a quantity determined at every point in space and time. While classical particle mechanics deals with a finite number of generalized coordinates $q_a(t)$, indexed by the label a , in field theory we are interested in the field dynamics where a and x are considered labels

Spin

- We can assume the ground state would be the entangled state of both. This creates a pull-push sequence that is important regarding entanglement; this creates a twisted treadmill track that provides infinite possibilities. This of course would cause Hilbert space which is a very small dimension (which is the next step) that would cause higher dimensional figures and color spaces.

Medius in action

- Similar to data processing, it works like a computer; it manipulates “raw data” like elementary particles in a quantum field. The CPU represents the current dependency between realities, with both realities being the core of the main process, the result will be the reality of changes occurring in both but with different effects with every action

Timeline

- Normal conversation would have a problem it would be able to perceive the future and the past at the same time. It would go like this (the receipt, the decept, the incept, and the except).

Topology

Chainmail-like formation with invisible link formation.

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